

Haem oxygenase (version 2019.4) in the IUPHAR/BPS Guide to Pharmacology Database

Timothy R. Billiar¹, Giuseppe Cirino², David Fulton³, Roberto Motterlini⁴, Andreas Papapetropoulos⁵ and Csaba Szabo⁶

1. University of Pittsburgh, USA
2. University of Naples-Federico II, Italy
3. Georgia Regents University, USA
4. University of Paris Est Creteil, France
5. University of Athens, Greece
6. University of Texas, USA

Abstract

Haem oxygenase (heme,hydrogen-donor:oxygen oxidoreductase (α -methene-oxidizing, hydroxylating)), [E.C. 1.14.99.3](#), converts [heme](#) into [biliverdin](#) and carbon monoxide, utilizing [NADPH](#) as cofactor.

Contents

This is a citation summary for Haem oxygenase in the [Guide to Pharmacology](#) database (GtoPdb). It exists purely as an adjunct to the database to facilitate the recognition of citations to and from the database by citation analyzers. Readers will almost certainly want to visit the relevant sections of the database which are given here under database links.

[GtoPdb](#) is an expert-driven guide to pharmacological targets and the substances that act on them. GtoPdb is a reference work which is most usefully represented as an on-line database. As in any publication this work should be appropriately cited, and the papers it cites should also be recognized. This document provides a citation for the relevant parts of the database, and also provides a reference list for the research cited by those parts.

Please note that the database version for the citations given in GtoPdb are to the most recent preceding version in which the family or its subfamilies and targets were substantially changed. The links below are to the current version. If you need to consult the cited version, rather than the most recent version, please contact the GtoPdb curators.

Database links

[Haem oxygenase](#)

<http://www.guidetopharmacology.org/GRAC/FamilyDisplayForward?familyId=278>

Enzymes

[HO1\(Haem oxygenase 1\)](#)

<http://www.guidetopharmacology.org/GRAC/ObjectDisplayForward?objectId=1441>

References

1. Araujo JA, Meng L, Tward AD, Hancock WW, Zhai Y, Lee A, Ishikawa K, Iyer S, Buelow R and Busuttil RW *et al.*. (2003) Systemic rather than local heme oxygenase-1 overexpression improves cardiac allograft outcomes in a new transgenic mouse. *J. Immunol.* **171**: 1572-80 [PMID:12874251]
2. Araujo JA, Zhang M and Yin F. (2012) Heme oxygenase-1, oxidation, inflammation, and atherosclerosis. *Front Pharmacol* **3**: 119 [PMID:22833723]
3. Drummond GS and Kappas A. (1981) Prevention of neonatal hyperbilirubinemia by tin protoporphyrin IX, a potent competitive inhibitor of heme oxidation. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **78**: 6466-70 [PMID:6947237]
4. Hayashi S, Omata Y, Sakamoto H, Higashimoto Y, Hara T, Sagara Y and Noguchi M. (2004) Characterization of rat heme oxygenase-3 gene. Implication of processed pseudogenes derived from heme oxygenase-2 gene. *Gene* **336**: 241-50 [PMID:15246535]
5. Romanoski CE, Che N, Yin F, Mai N, Pouldar D, Civelek M, Pan C, Lee S, Vakili L and Yang W *et al.*. (2011) Network for activation of human endothelial cells by oxidized phospholipids: a critical role of heme oxygenase 1. *Circ. Res.* **109**: e27-41 [PMID:21737788]
6. Vlahakis JZ, Kinobe RT, Bowers RJ, Brien JF, Nakatsu K and Szarek WA. (2006) Imidazole-dioxolane compounds as isozyme-selective heme oxygenase inhibitors. *J. Med. Chem.* **49**: 4437-41 [PMID:16821802]